

EXPERIMENTAL VIBRATIONS-BASED CHARACTERIZATION OF A COMPOSITE STIFFENED CURVED PANEL MANUFACTURED AS ONE PIECE FOR THE HULL OF A FAST BOAT

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ABSTRACT

This work presents some preliminary results on the development of a systematic methodology for model free multi-scale detection of structural damage and local material anomalies in complex composite materials ship structures. The core of the methodology is the collection of collocated acceleration signals in local and global regions of a prototype for complex structures encountered in naval and marine ship platforms. According to this approach, the structure is subjected to a protocol of a sequence of nondestructive pulse-like force excitation over a selected region while the acceleration response is collected with few sensors-located at strategic points-as a function of the location of the excitation source. This is an indirect space-time sampling of the transient dynamics of a continuous flexible structure. From a practical standpoint, it is quite attractive for it requires only few sensors and force actuators as opposed to actual space-time sampling requiring a network of distributed sensors and a large number of channels for data acquisition. We have found that the Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) modal shapes of simultaneously mined collocated acceleration databases are robust against errors in impact-induced force interrogation. By introducing a nonlinear logarithmic measure, we have found that the nodal points of the POD modal shapes process sensitivity signatures which are localized in space. This sensitivity detection result forms a focus for effective multi-scale structural anomaly detection with applications to condition monitoring of naval and aerospace complex structural systems.

1 INTRODUCTION

A challenging issue in assessment of damage in complex structural systems, such as stiffened composite panels manufactured as a whole structure [1], is whether a reliable nondestructive detection of hidden damage in critical areas, such as joints, is possible by relying on current sensor and actuator technologies, especially those based on piezoelectricity. The usual practice in modern vibrations-based structural health monitoring is to collect information on dynamics at few points in the structure under consideration [2]. This approach has inherent limitations, such as limited information on the dynamics. A way to obtain rich dynamics-based information for damage detection is to collect spatially distributed acceleration time series. However, this avenue requires expensive instrumentation-not easily accommodated for the typical complex structure. Moreover, the structure geometry complexity is an obstacle in trying to extract from propagating elastic waves and free vibrations information on

damage. The current wave-based monitoring research activities are based on theoretical knowledge on wave propagation in structural element of quite simple geometry [2]. Here we present a way to mine space-time information on dynamics and fully exploit this information for damage detection and in general for identification of complex structural systems, especially those manufactured as one piece from composite materials. By using few sensors and a force actuator, we have measured the transverse acceleration field of a composite ship hull segment undergoing a mix of elastic wave propagation, free vibrations and rigid body motions. The mined space-time databases of the transverse acceleration field are processed properly by means of advanced proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) tools. The basic problem that we have addressed at a preliminary level is the spatial quantification of the sensitivity of the POD modal shapes on the uncontrolled uncertainties produced naturally in creating interrogation impulsive forces by modal hammers furnished by mature piezoelectric technology.

2 MINING COLLOCATED ACCELERATION SIGNALS IN COMPLEX STRUCTURES

Figure 1 is a schematic of a complex panel like structure. It is characterized by considerable geometric complexity: it is curved and it is reinforced by a long hollow stiffener. For purposes focused on system identification and damage detection, this complex flexible structure is interrogated by an impulsive force applied along the local normal to a specified interrogation material curve. Information on the induced transverse acceleration is mined by three accelerometers arranged into a local triad (Fig. 1a) and separately into a global one (Fig. 1b). Figure 2 depicts a physical complex ship structure manufactured as one piece from polymeric composite material. This complex structure is manufactured as one piece in a mold by an advanced manufacturing process used to build fast boat hull structures. It is a curved trapezoidal panel with opposite sides: 2830 mm x 2410 mm and 1210 mm x 680 mm; and reinforced by a large interior box like stiffener: 2370 mm x 420 mm curved length. We select a material curve on the front surface and we mark a number of $N=27$ points along it, all of them equally spaced at about 100mm. The interrogation curve follows a geodesic of the surface. A triad of high performance piezoelectric mono-axial accelerometers is arranged in a local region with complex geometry (Fig 3a). The region contains part of the stiffener. The triad of sensors is arranged in a global region along the curved box stiffener. A high performance modal hammer is used to induce impulsive forces normal (z -direction) to the panel surface at the marked points.

Figure 1: Schematic of a large scale structural element with intrinsic geometric complexity stemming from a curved shell surface reinforced by a box type stiffener. Three sensors are used to mine

information on the free vibration dynamics induced by a pulse applied along the local normal to the surface.

We have mined the following information on free propagating elastic waves and free vibrations : (a) a set of interrogation impulsive forces distributed over the interrogation material curve (Fig. 2), (b) three simultaneous sets of acceleration signals detected by the three sensors either in local triangular configuration (Fig. 3a) or in geodesic global configuration (Fig. 3b). The acceleration signals detected by a fixed sensor as a function of the location of injection of the interrogation impulsive force shall be referred to as a *collocated* space-time database. Collocated databases are very rich in spatial and temporal information on the dynamics of a flexible structure [4,6].

The objective of this work is to investigate whether local and global triads of collocated databases could be useful tools for multi-scale system identification and multi-scale damage detection in complex structures without explicit use of a model that describes their geometry. The challenges here are (1) the fact that we do not have a computational model of the physical structure and (2) the fact that the set of interrogation impulsive forces are produced indirectly via impact and thus random uncertainties enter naturally. Thus, the very basic issue that should be addressed is the quantification of sensitivity of the ensembles of collocated acceleration signals on the random variations of the ensembles of interrogation forces.

Figure 2: Photographic views of an actual composite materials ship hull structure reinforced by a box type longitudinal stiffener as part of the hull of a fast boat under commercial production. It has been manufactured as one piece in a mold. It is used as a prototypical complex structural system to mine collocated acceleration signals using proved sensor and actuator technology.

Figure 3: Composite ship panel instrumented with a triad of high performance piezoelectric accelerometers. (a) Local triad encompasses a region with complex geometry. (b) Global triad

encompasses a global region of simple geometry (longitudinal surface of a uniform stiffener). The panel is excited by an impulsive force applied along a specified interrogation horizontal curve lying on the exterior surface (Fig.2).

3 ADVANCED PROCESSING OF COLLOCATED SENSORY INFORMATION

The fixed accelerometer detects signals along the local normal vector as a function of the location of the injected impulsive force. On the basis of pure theoretical mechanics fundamental facts, we assume tentatively that the collection of signals mined by the fixed sensor is parameterized in space by the location where the impulsive force is applied [4]. Note that the sensing direction of the sensor follows the time varying direction of the local normal to the surface []. This collocated space-time information on coupled dynamics will be interpreted in term of physics by subjecting it to an advanced signal processing of space-time distribute information. The advanced processing is furnished by the POD (proper orthogonal decomposition), or PCA (principal components analysis) transform, for coupled multi-axial dynamical processes [3].

Here we have three simultaneous collocated databases for the transverse component of the acceleration vector field: one local and one global. The acceleration vector field of the complex ship panel can be resolved into three locally mutually normal components. Represented mathematically as an $M \times N$ matrix \mathbb{A} , the properly normalized collocated database is transformed into a definite number of POD (proper orthogonal decomposition) modes. Mathematically a POD mode in flexible structural dynamics [] is formed by the product of a modal participation factor $\sqrt{\lambda_k}$, the time modulation vector $\hat{\mathbf{Q}}_k$, and the space modulation vector $\hat{\mathbf{\Phi}}_k$:

$$\mathbb{A}_k \equiv \sqrt{\lambda_k} \hat{\mathbf{Q}}_k \hat{\mathbf{\Phi}}_k^T \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times N}, \quad k = 1, \dots, K^* \quad (1)$$

The energy-time-space pattern, Eq. 1, is identified with a stationary direction-thus qualifying to as being an intrinsic characteristic feature-associated with the cloud formed by the collocated database when viewed as a geometric object in the appropriate mathematical linear space. The POD or PCA transform results into the most optimal partition of the collocated database energy over its intrinsic bi-orthogonal modes, the latter providing compressed critical information.

The level of spatio-temporal coherence of the database is determined by the law according to which the database energy, Eq. (3), is partitioned over the wave number space of the intrinsic POD modes. It is determined elegantly by examining closely the normalized POD energy spectrum:

$$\hat{\Lambda} \equiv \{\hat{\lambda}_1, \hat{\lambda}_2, \dots, \hat{\lambda}_k, \dots, \hat{\lambda}_{K^*}\}, \quad \hat{\lambda}_k \equiv \frac{\lambda_k}{E(\mathbb{A})} \quad (2)$$

$$E(\mathbb{A}) \equiv \|\mathbb{A}\|^2 \equiv \frac{2}{M-1} \times \frac{2}{N-1} \text{tr}(\mathbb{A}^T \mathbb{A}) \quad (3)$$

The ensembles of the impact-generated interrogation force signals and the corresponding ensembles of collocated acceleration signals will be evaluated as dynamics information distributed over the space-time domain by considering the properties of their intrinsic POD modes. *The evaluation aims at determining whether the pulse-based collocated information on the dynamics of a complex composite materials continuum is useful for system identification and damage-anomaly detection.*

3.1 EVALUATION OF THE INTERROGATION IMPULSIVE FORCES

The set of the modal hammer-generated forces is a sequence of randomly generated signals in the sense that the maximum value should be within a zone about a mean value. Moreover, the time waveform of the normalized signals should stem as small variations from a mother waveform. We

examine to see if this is the situation here. In particular, for three generated samples of the interrogation impulsive forces we have the fact that the *average-standard deviation* of the maxima of the forces is as follows (Newton): *Test1: 32.670686-4.875549*, *Test2: 32.850270-4.665984*, and *Test3: 32.133254-4.891021*. The analogous computed quantities of the impulse of the forces are as follows (Newton-seconds): *Test1: 0.060522-0.00676*, *Test2: 0.060693-0.007141*, *Test3: 0.0596341-0.006920*. The above estimations indicate that the standard deviation of the maximum value of the pulse is about 15% of the average value whereas that for the impulse is about 10%. So we have a natural uncertainty of the impulsive force generated manually by the modal hammer. The challenge is-despite this uncertainty-to investigate whether the collocated acceleration signals can form tools for a model free identification of natural vibration properties (normal modes, dissipation factors) of a complex structure with particular interest in the area of vibration-based assessment of structural integrity of composite materials structures tailored for ship design. In the sequel, we isolate the time waveform of the typical force signal by dividing the time series of the signal with the norm squared value. We consider at least three samples of interrogation set forces. After proper normalization signal-by-signal, we analyze them as a whole by considering their POD intrinsic modes. Presenting the POD energy spectrum, Fig. 4a reveals that the typical sample of the interrogation forces is dominated literally by a single POD mode, capturing more than 99.500% of the ensemble energy. The corresponding modal shape, Fig. 4b, is uniform whereas the companion modal amplitude, Fig. 4c, is a pulse of standard waveform, the mother pulse. The single mode dominance indicates that the impact response of the composite material panel is a position independent pulse. This result is not trivial since the impulsive force is dictated by the physics of local impact of a concentrated elastic hard mass on another flexible continuum composite materials structure which could have been damaged by surface cracks and corrosion.

Figure 4: POD analysis of the typical ensemble of interrogation impulsive forces generated by manual impact of a high performance modal hammer along $N=27$ nearly equally spaced points on a longitudinal interrogation curve. (a) Single mode POD energy spectrum, (b) uniform modal shape, (c) pulse distribution of the modal amplitude.

3.2 EVALUATION OF THE COLLOCATED ACCELERATION SIGNALS

Next we consider the ensembles of collocated acceleration signals. For each sensor in the triad, we have three samples of collocated acceleration signals associated respectively with the three samples of the impact-based set of excitation forces. The databases are normalized properly to take care of the random fluctuation of the norm value of the excitation impulses. Figure 5 shows the POD energy spectra for the local array and the global array formed by the three sensors. The experimental error is quite small. It is clear that the typical POD spectrum is a fast decaying function of the POD modal number. It is underlined by an exponential law behavior. If the acceleration dynamics process of the structure were random the partition of the energy should be even according to the classical statistical mechanics laws. Because of the nearly exponential law behavior of the POD energy spectrum, we can talk of reduced order dynamics. In fact, the first 10 POD modes contain about 94-95% of the database energy.

Compressed spatial information, thus critical in a sense, is contained in the POD modal shapes. Figure 6 shows the modal shape of the dominant POD mode. These are the averaged shapes. For each sensor, we have analyzed three sample databases. The experimental error is quite small. Its value is robust in the sense that it resides within the zone 0.002-0.050. Note that the modal shapes have unit norm values. It is remarkable that the modal shapes of the databases associated with the global sensor arrangement are nearly the same, Fig. 6b, whereas those for the local triangular arrangement are quite different, Fig. 6a. We conjecture that this reflects the complexity of the geometry of the region covered by the sensor triad.

Figure 5: The POD normalized energy spectra of the collocated acceleration databases mined simultaneously by a communicating triad (black, red, green) of accelerometers. Top-sensors forming a local triangle arrangement. Bottom- sensors covering a global material strip lying on the longitudinal box stiffener.

Figure 6: The unit shape of the first dominant POD mode of the collocated acceleration databases. (a) Sensors in local triangle arrangement (Fig. 3a). (b) Sensors covering a global material strip lying on the longitudinal box stiffener (Fig. 3b).

4 DISTRIBUTED ERROR SENSITIVITY INDEX

Our goal is to pave a way for model free multi-axial and multi-scale damage detection in complex ship structures composed of different materials including both monolithic and composite ones. Towards this end, we need to gain knowledge on the robustness of the POD modal shapes against the uncertainty stemming from the set of interrogation forces. Random pointwise errors are introduced because the impulsive force is created manually via the dynamical process of impact of a concentrated mass on a distributed one over a complex region of the physical space. The impulsive excitation involves initially elastic wave propagation and finally settled free vibrations. It is well-known that waves interact with the inhomogeneities formed by damage such as cracks and corrosion. Having available three samples of collocated space-time information at the site of each sensor in the triad, we define the vector logarithmic variation of the k th POD modal shape as follows [5]:

$$\delta_{\log} \hat{\Phi}_k^{[T_2/T_1]} \equiv \left\{ \Phi_{kn}^{[T_2/T_1]} \right\}_{n=1}^N, \quad \Phi_{kn}^{[T_2/T_1]} \equiv 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{|\Phi_{kn}^{[T_2]}|}{|\Phi_{kn}^{[T_1]}|} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$\delta_{\log} \hat{\Phi}_k^{[T_3/T_1]} \equiv \left\{ \Phi_{kn}^{[T_3/T_1]} \right\}_{n=1}^N, \quad \Phi_{kn}^{[T_3/T_1]} \equiv 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{|\Phi_{kn}^{[T_3]}|}{|\Phi_{kn}^{[T_1]}|} \right) \quad (5)$$

Unit vectors $\hat{\Phi}_k^{[T_2]} = \hat{\Phi}_k^{[T_1]} + \delta \hat{\Phi}_k^{[T_1/T_2]}$ and $\hat{\Phi}_k^{[T_3]} = \hat{\Phi}_k^{[T_1]} + \delta \hat{\Phi}_k^{[T_1/T_3]}$ denote the POD modal shape for databases-test2, test3; whereas $\hat{\Phi}_k^{[T_1]}$ denotes the corresponding POD modal shape for database-test1. As supported by the experiments, these vectors are expressed as small variations of a reference vector. In view of this relation, the two samples of the distributed sensitivity index take the following forms:

$$\Phi_{kn}^{[T_2/T_1]} = 20 \log_{10} \left(\left| 1 + \frac{\delta \Phi_{kn}^{[T_1/T_2]}}{\Phi_{kn}^{[T_1]}} \right| \right) \quad (6)$$

$$\Phi_{kn}^{[T_3/T_1]} = 20 \log_{10} \left(\left| 1 + \frac{\delta \Phi_{kn}^{[T_1/T_3]}}{\Phi_{kn}^{[T_1]}} \right| \right) \quad (7)$$

The ideal situation occurs when the SI is distributed uniformly at precisely zero dB level. In principle, this could occur whenever the structure is ideally linear and the force is applied normally to the surface. However, here we cannot have the ideal situation, necessarily accompanying a healthy structure tested under zero experimental errors. Figures 7-9 present the distribution of the SI for the 1st POD modal shapes of the three collocated databases. We have the remarkable result that the nodal points of the POD modal shape are sensitive to the interrogation force uncertainty and that this sensitivity appears as a localized spatial function in the regions containing the nodal points. Moreover, this localized sensitivity remains invariant in the sense that it appears to be qualitatively the same in two different samples for the typical collocated space-time database.

Figure 7: Three samples {test1, test2, tes3} of collocated acceleration information mined by the accelerometer at site 1 of the local triad arrangement (Fig. 3a). (a) Small variation of the shape of the 1st dominant POD mode due to interrogation force uncertainty. (b) A computed pair of samples of the distribution of the sensitivity index.

Figure 8: Three samples {test1, test2, tes3} of collocated information mined by the accelerometer at site 2 of the local triad arrangement (Fig. 3a). (a) Small variation of the shape of the 1st dominant POD mode due to interrogation force uncertainty. (b) A computed pair of samples of the distribution of the sensitivity index.

Figure 9: Three samples {test1, test2, tes3} of collocated acceleration information mined by the accelerometer at site 3 of the local triad arrangement (Fig. 3a). (a) Small variation of the shape of the 1st dominant POD mode due to interrogation force uncertainty. (b) A computed pair of samples of the distribution of the sensitivity index.

5 CONCLUSIONS

We have presented a methodology involving few sensors and an actuator-as data mining tools of piezoelectricity-based sensor technology-to collect distributed in space-time information on the free vibrations of a physical complex ship structure composed of composite materials. The core of the methodology is the use of three accelerometers in local triangular and extended geodesic configurations. The collocated elastic wave propagation and settled vibrations information is rendered useful by considering the intrinsic proper orthogonal decomposition (POD) modes. We find that the dominant POD modal shapes of databases collected by a triad of sensors contains critical information on the geometry complexity of local and global regions of a complex ship panel structure. A remarkable result is the fact that the POD modal shapes contain critical areas sensitive to small variations of the set of interrogation forces. These critical areas contain nodal points like those encountered in natural normal modes of vibration. The mining of collocated free vibrations signals and the POD-based advanced signal processing has potential applications to quality monitoring in

manufacturing of large scale composite material structures and damage detection and dissipation estimation for structural health monitoring purposes of complex composite structures in service.

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